

A CASE REPORT ON SEVERE ANAEMIA WITH IRON DEFICIENCY AND IT'S MANAGEMENT

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Received: Apr 04, 2026

Accepted: Apr 28, 2026

Published: Apr 30, 2026

Abstract: A common but potentially fatal haematological condition, severe iron deficiency anaemia is characterized by significantly lower haemoglobin levels and a compromised blood's ability to carry oxygen. Chronic blood loss, insufficient nutrition, malabsorption or elevated physiological demands are frequently the causes. Fatigue, wide spread weakness, Pallor, dyspnoea, dizziness, and decreased exercise tolerance are common presentations. Low haemoglobin, decreased serum ferritin, decreased serum iron, increased total iron-binding capacity, and microcytic hypochromic red blood cells are among the laboratory results. Severe cases may result in decreased immunity, heart problems, and a lower quality of life if they are not treated. In addition to iron replacement therapy either oral or Parenteral, depending on severity and patient tolerance management entails determining and treating the underlying cause. When haemoglobin levels are extremely low, a blood transfusion may be necessary.

Key words: Iron deficiency/anaemia, microcytic hypochromic anemia, chronic blood loss.

1. INTRODUCTION :

Iron deficiency anemia is marked by a significant decrease in hemoglobin severe levels caused by insufficient iron, leading to reduced red blood cells production and diminished oxygen transport in the blood. Symptoms include severe fatigue, pale skin, chest pain, Shortness of breath and rapid heart beat. Treatment involves iron supplementation, addressing the route cause, and in severe cases, intravenous iron or blood transfusions. Anaemia is a group of conditions characterized by lowered haemoglobin or circulating red blood cells, which impair oxygen delivery¹⁴⁷. Causes encompass blood loss, increased destruction of RBC's, or inadequate RBC production. It may also signal underlying health issues such as cancer or other systemic diseases. Rapid diagnosis of the cause crucial because anaemia frequently indicates underlying pathology.

1.1 PHARMACOEPIDEMOLOGY:

In developing nations like India, where chronic blood loss and nutritional deficiencies are prevalent, severe iron deficiency anaemia(IDA) continues to be a major public health concern. It affects a significant percentage of adult males and females and accounts for almost half of cases of anaemia. The patient's presentation in this instance exhibits common pharmacoepidemiological patterns, such as delayed diagnosis and severe symptoms necessitating medical attention⁶. The cornerstone of treatment is oral iron therapy, but real-world data show difficulties like poor adherence, gastrointestinal side effects, and delayed response. Severe iron deficiency reveals a substantial global burden, with iron deficiency being the primary cause of approximately 50% of all anaemia cases. While global anaemia prevalence is estimated at 24.3% to 25%.

1.2 AETIOLOGY :

Severe iron deficiency anaemia is caused likely due to prolonged imbalance between iron intake and loss leading to depleted body iron stores. The most likely causes are inadequate dietary iron intake and possible chronic blood loss, which are common contributors in adult patients. The condition may have been aggravated further by poor nutritional status, reduced consumption of iron rich foods and impaired absorption.

1.3 SIGNS AND SYMPTOMS :

The patient presented with classical clinical features of severe iron deficiency anaemia like generalized weakness, fatigue and reduced exercise tolerance of one month duration. He also complained of grade 2 dyspnoea, which suggested compromised oxygen carrying capacity. These findings are consistent with macrocytic hypochromic anaemia and are largely due to hypoxia of the tissue due to reduced levels of haemoglobin.

1.4 PATHOGENESIS :

Iron deficiency anaemia occurs when there is a negative iron imbalance caused by reduced iron intake, increased physiological requirements, chronic blood loss or impaired absorption. This results in depletion of iron stores in organs like liver, spleen and bone marrow, which is reflected by low ferritin levels. As iron becomes less available, the synthesis of haemoglobin is inhibited, leading to decreased serum iron and less red blood cell production. As a result, the bone marrow produces hypochromic microcytic RBCs with less capacity to carry oxygen. The resulting decrease in oxygen deliver to tissues causes tissue hypoxia which clinically presents as fatigue, pallor, weakness, breathlessness, tachycardia.

fig 1: pathogenesis of iron deficiency anaemia.

2. CASE REPORT :

2.1 SUBJECTIVE EVIDENCE :

A 45 year male patient was admitted in hospital with the chief complaints of generalized body weakness per 1month, shortness of breath (grade 2) on exertion for 1 month, fatigue and burning sensation on micturition. The patient reported that the weakness was progressive in nature and had affected his activities of daily living. Hello also reported easy fatigability, reduced exercise tolerance and occasional dizziness.

2.2.OBJECTIVE EVIDENCE :

The complete blood picture (CBP) revealed a haemoglobin level of 6.2g/dl suggestive of severe anaemia. The mean corpuscular volume (MCV) is 59.5fl and mean corpuscular haemoglobin(MCH) is 26.7pg which is suggestive of microcytic hypochromic anemia. These laboratory findings are consistent with severe anaemia.

2.3 DIAGNOSIS:

Hemogram (Complete Blood Picture)

The patient had a significantly low haemoglobin levels of 6.2g/dl on hemogram which is suggestive of severe anaemia. Red cell indices reveal low mean corpuscular volume (MCV)of 59.5FL and low mean corpuscular haemoglobin (MCH)of 26.7pg.This suggest that red blood cells are hypochromic (less haemoglobin) and microcytic (smaller in size)

Iron Profile

The iron profile in iron deficiency anaemia generally shows markedly lowered serum ferritin levels reflecting the depleted iron stores of the body, and serum iron levels are also significantly lower. In response to low iron availability, the body attempt to upregulate iron transport by increasing the total iron binding capacity (TIBC). Decreased transferrin saturation due to low circulating iron serum ferritin is the best and most sensitive index for the determining iron insufficiency.

Reticulocyte Count

The reticulocyte count shows how the bone marrow react to anaemia. Even though the patient has very low levels of red blood cells, the reticulocyte count should be low or abnormally normal. This means that red blood cells are not being made as quickly as they should be. This happens because iron is needed to make red blood cells and haemoglobin. If you don't have enough iron , the marrow can't make new red blood cells as quickly as it should.

Bone Marrow Aspiration and Biopsy

In iron deficiency anaemia, a bone marrow examination usually shows erythroid hyperplasia, which means that the body is making more red blood cell precursors to make up the for the lack of red blood cells. Iron staining (Prussian blue stain) shows that macrophages and developing the erythroblasts have a little or no iron stores. The normal pattern of cell maturation is usually normoblastic.

Peripheral Blood Smear (PBS)

A peripheral blood smear test shows typical changes in the shape of red blood cells. The cell look microcytic and hypochromic, and the center is more pale. There is a significant anisocytosis (variation in size) and poikilocytosis (variations in shape), along with the presence of pencil-shaped cells or elliptocytes, which are characteristic of iron deficiency anaemia. These morphological abnormalities indicate impaired haemoglobin synthesis are aberrant erythropoiesis.

3. MANAGEMENT:

3.1. STANDARD THERAPY:

Oral iron therapy:

The recommended elemental iron dose for treating iron deficiency anaemia in adults is 120mg per day for three months, whereas in children it is 3 mg/kg/day, up to a maximum of 60 mg daily. An increase in haemoglobin of about 1g/dl after one month of therapy indicates an adequate response and supports the diagnosis. In adults, iron supplementation should be continued for three months after correction of anaemia to fully restore iron stores. Adherence to oral iron therapy may be limited by gastrointestinal adverse effects such as epigastric discomfort, nausea diarrhoea, and constipation. Taking iron with meals can reduce these symptoms, although this may decrease absorption by approximately 40%.

Parenteral iron therapy :

Parenteral therapy is recommended for patient with iron Deficiency anaemia who cannot tolerate or adequately absorb oral iron, such as those with gastrectomy, bariatric or small-bowel surgery. Serious reactions occur in up to 0.7% of patients receiving iron dextran, whereas iron sucrose and sodium ferric gluconate have better bioavailability and lower risk of severe anaphylaxis. About 35% of patient on iron sucrose experience mild effect such as headache, nausea, or diarrhoea.

Form	Formulation	Elemental Iron	Adult dosage
Oral			
• Ferrous fumarate	324mg tablet	106mg	1 tablet twice per day
• Ferrous gluconate	300mg tablet	38mg	1-3 tablet 2 or 3 times per day
• Ferrous sulfate	325 mg tablet	65mg	1 tablet 3 times per day

Intravenous			Based on body weight and amount of desired change in haemoglobin*
• Sodium gluconate	Solution for injection	12.5 mg/ml	
• Iron dextran	Solution for injection	50mg/ml	
• Iron sucrose	Solution for injection	20mg/ml	
• Ferumoxytol	Solution for injection	30mg/ml	

Table 1: Standard therapy

*---Elemental iron (mg) = $50 \times (0.442[\text{desired haemoglobin level in g/l} - \text{observed haemoglobin level in g/l}] \times \text{lean body weight} + 0.26 \times \text{lean body weight})$.

3.2. CURRENT THERAPY

Brand Medication	Generic name &Category	Dose/ Frequency	Mechanism of action
Tab. Orofer	Ferric carboxy maltose- Iron supplement.	10 mg/PO/OD	It works by supplying elemental iron that gets absorbed in intestine & incorporated into haemoglobin.
Syp. Citralka	Disodium hydrogen citrate-Urinary alkalinizer.	10 ml in 1 glass of water	It works by metabolizing into bicarbonate in the body, which alkalinizes urine, reduces acidity

Tab. Pulmoclear	Acebrophylline, Guaifenesin and Terbutaline Sulphate- Bronchodilator and mucolytics.	100mg/PO/OD	It works by breaking down thick mucous & reducing its viscosity.
Tab.Zofer	Ondansetron- antiemetic	4mg/PO/OD	It works by selectively blocking serotonin(5HT3) receptors in the CTZ and GI tract.
Tab.PAN	Pantoprazole-proton pump inhibitor.	40mg/PO/OD	It “irreversibly inhibits the H ⁺ /K ⁺ ATPase” in gastric parietal cells, leading to prolonged suppression of acid production.

Table: current treatment

PATIENT COUNSELLING:

4. Management of side effects:

During treatment, patient may experience side effects such as constipation, nausea, abdominal discomfort, dark stools, or metallic taste. These can be managed by increase fluid and fiber intake, taking iron after food if gastric irritation occurs, and maintaining proper oral hygiene. Concomitant medications such as Pantaprazole may cause headache or diarrhoea, while Ondansetron may lead to constipation; these effects can usually be controlled with adequate hydration and dietary adjustment.

Monitoring:

Regular monitoring is essential to evaluate treatment response and ensure safety. This includes periodic assessment of haemoglobin levels, serum ferritin, and iron profile to assess improvement in iron stores, along with reticulocyte count as an early indicator of response. Clinical improvement is reflected by reduced fatigue, improved physical activity, and better overall well -being.

Lifestyle and nutrition:

Diet : The patient should ensure adequate rest with 7-8hours of sleep and engage in mild physical activity. Proper hydration should be maintained with sufficient fluid intake. The diet should be rich

in iron, including heme source such as red meat, liver, poultry and fish, and nonheme sources like green leafy vegetables, lentils bean, nuts, and iron- fortified cereals. To enhance iron absorption, vitamin C- rich foods such as citrus, guava, amla, and tomatoes. Should be consumed along with meals. At the same time, tea, coffee, and calcium rich meal as they inhibit iron absorption.

Control and Control : Correction and control of iron deficiency require consistent adherence to iron supplementation as prescribed, usually continued for 3-6 months ever after improvement in symptoms to replenish iron stores.

5. CONCLUSION :

Severe iron deficiency anaemia continues to be a major clinical and public health problem, especially in developing countries. The patient's condition was well managed by appropriate iron supplementation, supportive therapy and close monitoring. Long-term management and prevention of the recurrence requires identification of underlying causes such as inadequate dietary intake and potential chronic blood loss. Patient counselling in medication adherence, dietary and lifestyle changes was an important factor in improving treatment outcomes. Regular follow up and monitoring of haemoglobin and iron parameters are required to ensure recovery and restoration of the iron stores.

5.1 FINAL CLINICAL OUTLOOK:

The general clinical picture of Severe iron deficiency anaemia is usually good if diagnosed early and managed properly. Here, the patient is expected to have gradual improvement in haemoglobin levels with an approximate increase 1g/dl per week or month depending on therapy adherence and absorption. Symptoms such as fatigue, dyspnoea and weakness usually improve within a few weeks of starting treatment. Iron supplementation should be continued for a minimum of 3 to 6 months to restore depleted iron stores and prevent relapse.

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